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DIVERSITY, RELATIVE ABUNDANCE AND SOME BIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF FISHES IN GEBA AND SOR RIVERS, BARO-AKOBO BASIN, SOUTHWEST ETHIOPIA

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ABSTRACT

Diversity, relative abundance and some biological aspects of fishes in Geba and Sor Rivers were studied using gill nets (6, 8, 10 and 12cm stretched mesh sizes) and hooks. Samples of fish were collected in wet (October to November 2012) and dry (February to March 2013) seasons. A total of 348 fish specimens were collected from both rivers at both seasons. Nine fish species were identified which were included in six genera and four families. The represented families include Mormyridae, Cyprinidae, Bagridae and Cichlidae. The family Cyprinidae was the most dominant with respect to number of species consisting of six species (66.7%). The diversity of fish species in Geba River ($H' = 1.50$) was higher than that of Sor River ($H' = 1.10$). The fish diversity of Geba and Sor Rivers is less compared to most studied Ethiopian rivers. *Labeobarbus intermedius* (60.72%IRI), *Labeobarbus nedgia* (16.83%IRI) and *Labeo cylindricus* (14.66%IRI) were the most abundant fish species. The abundance of fish specimens in dry season was higher than in wet season. The length-weight relationships for these species were found to be curvilinear. The mean FCF for *Labeobarbus intermedius*, *Labeobarbus nedgia* and *Labeo cylindricus* were 1.21, 1.02 and 1.21 in Geba and Sor Rivers, respectively. There was significant variation (ANOVA, $P < 0.05$) in FCF of *Labeo cylindricus* in the two seasons. However, variations were insignificant (ANOVA, $P > 0.05$) for the *Labeobarbus intermedius* and *Labeobarbus nedgia* in wet and dry seasons. In both rivers females were more numerous than males and statistically significant (Chi-square, $P < 0.05$). Further investigation on the fish diversity especially on the tributaries of these rivers and socio-economic aspects of the two rivers is recommended.

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INTRODUCTION

Ethiopia could be called the “water tower of northeastern Africa” on a continent where aridity is the rule. Inland water bodies of Ethiopia are estimated to be about 7400 km² of lake area and about 7000 km of river length (Wood and Talling, 1988), with diversified fish species. The first review on Ethiopian freshwater by Shibru Tedla (1973) listed 93 fish species. Abebe Getahun and Stiassny (1998) undertook extensive field work and revisional studies in a large number of the country’s drainage basins from 1995 to 1997. They identified 65 species belonging to 19 genera and 9 families with large proportion of the species coming from the cyprinid family and occurring in Abay (Blue Nile) drainage basin. Review papers by Abebe Getahun (2003 and 2007), mentioned the occurrence of 153 and 152 valid indigenous fish species and subspecies in 25 and 24 families in Ethiopian freshwater systems respectively and also 10 exotic and 40-41 endemic species and subspecies were described.

According to Golubstov and Darkov (2008) there are 113 fish species belonging to 66 genera and 26 families within the White Nile drainage basin, 77 species in 37 genera and 16 families within Blue Nile drainage basin, the Omo-Turkana drainage basin comprises 76-79 species within 42 genera and 20 families, the Atbara-Tekeze drainage basin has 34 species in 22 genera and 10 families, Shebelle-Juba drainage basin also contain 33 species belonging to 21 genera and 12 families while the Rift valley drainage basin has 28-31 species of fish in 18 genera and 11 families.

According to Roberts (1975) the freshwater fish fauna of Ethiopia contains a mixture of Nilo-Sudanic, East African and endemic forms. The Nilo-Sudanic forms are related to West African fishes, hence supporting the hypothesis that the Nile has been historically connected to the central and West African river systems (Abebe Getahun, 2002).

Generally, the knowledge of the diversity of the Ethiopian fish fauna is far from complete. Many of the drainage basins, especially the rivers, are not exhaustively explored (Abebe Getahun, 2007). No detailed study has been made on estimation of the potentials of Ethiopian rivers, which are supposed to be economically important. Geba and Sor Rivers are among such rivers that have been poorly explored. To this effect there was no exhaustive systematic research has been done on the diversity, abundance and biology of fishes in Geba and Sor Rivers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the study area

The study was conducted at two sites of Illubabor Zone, Metu and Yayu districts, southwestern Ethiopia. Metu district is one of the twenty-three districts in Illubabor Zone in Oromia Regional State some 600 km of Addis Ababa (Fig.1). The mean annual maximum and minimum temperature of Metu District is 27.33°C and 11.21°C, respectively. The mean annual rainfall of the District is 1427.17 mm/year, with high variation from year to year. Yayu district is located in Illubabor Zone of Oromia Regional State, at 550 km to southwest of Addis Ababa (Fig. 1). The mean maximum and minimum annual temperatures of Yayu district is 29.07°C and 14.13°C, respectively. The mean annual rainfall of the District is 1563 mm/year, with high variation from year to year. The rainfall patterns of the districts are uni-modal, with low rainfall during January and February and the highest rainfall between June and August (National Meteorological Agency, Jimma Branch, 2013). Eight sampling sites were selected which are accessible to road, slow flowing and shallow water from Geba and Sor Rivers (Fig. 1, Table 1). All sampling sites except S1 have clear water, gravel, sandy and rocky substratum. *Ficus species*, *Coffea arabica*, *Croton macrostachyus* and *Schefflera abyssinica* are among the dominant vegetation area. Colobus monkey and Vervet monkey were common around sampling sites

Figure 1. Map of the study sites.

Table 1. Sampling sites, their codes, habitat type, width of the river and coordinates of Sor and Geba Rivers.

Site	Code	Habitat type	Width (m)	Coordinate (3D GPS)	Altitude (m asl)
Hora site	S1	Turbid water, gravel and muddy	32	78°61'43"N 92°19'86"E	1552
At the bridge from Metu to Alge	S2	Clear water, gravel, sandy and rocky	30	78°61'31"N 91°94'76"E	1554
Lakata site	S3	Clear water, gravel and rocky	33	78°87'28"N 91°83'77"E	1554
Moges site	S4	Clear water, gravel and rocky	33.70	78°97'36"N 91°71'70"E	1556
Doko site	G1	Clear water, gravel and rocky	35	80°91'53"N 92°75'01"E	1241
At the bridge from Yayu to Doreni district	G2	Clear water, gravel and rocky	33	80°81'81"N 92°69'82"E	1252
Below the bridge from Yayu to Doreni district	G3	Clear water, gravel, sandy and rocky	40	80°67'25"N 92°65'77"E	1254
At the bridge from Metu to Alge District	G4	Clear water, gravel and rocky	29	79°13'10"N 93°83'87"E	1149

Samples were collected in wet season (October to November 2012) and the dry season (February to March 2013). Each site was sampled two times (one in wet and the other in dry season) using gillnet of various mesh sizes (6, 8, 10 and 12 cm stretched mesh) and hooks. Gillnets were set late in the afternoon and then collected in the next day. Hooks were also used by selecting an appropriate site. Immediately after capture, total length (to the nearest 0.1 cm), and total weight (to the nearest 0.1g) of all specimens were measured at the sampling sites. Fish specimens from each species were preserved in 10% formalin solution and transported to the department of biology, Jimma University, for further investigation.

Identification

Identification of specimens were made to species level by using taxonomic keys found in Shibru Tedla (1973), Boulenger, G. (1909,1911,1915 & 1916), Golubtsov *et al.* (1995), Stiassny and Abebe Getahun (2007) and Redeat Habteselassie (2012).

Diversity Index

Shannon - Weiner diversity index (H') was used for estimating the diversity of fish species for each sampling site and the whole rivers (Begon *et al.*, 1990). Shannon - Weiner diversity index (H') was calculated using the equation:

$$H' = - \sum_{i=1}^S \frac{n_i}{N} \ln n_i/N$$

Where, \sum = sum from species 1 to species S
 n_i = number of individuals of species "i"
 N = total number of individuals of all species
 S = total number of species
 H' = the Shannon- Weiner Diversity Index

Relative Abundance

Estimation of relative abundance of fishes in Geba and Sor Rivers were made by comparing the relative catch both in number and weight in the total sampling. IRI is a measure of the relative abundance or commonness of the species based on number and weight of individuals in catches, as well as their frequency of occurrence (Kolding, 1989, 1999) and computed as:

$$\% IRI = \frac{(\% W_i + \% N_i) \times \% F_i}{\sum_{j=1}^s (\% W_j + \% N_j) \times \% F_j} \times 100$$

Where, $j=1$ to S , $\% W_i$ and $\% N_i$ are percentage weight and number of each species of total catch, respectively; $\% F_i$ is percentage frequency of occurrence of each species in total samplings. $\% W_j$ and $\% N_j$ are percentage weight and number of total species of total catch, respectively. $\% F_j$ is percentage frequency of occurrence of total species in total number of samplings and S is the total number of species.

Length-Weight Relationship: Following Bagenal and Tesch (1978), the relationship between total length and total weight of the dominant fish species of the Geba and Sor Rivers were calculated using power function.

$$W = a (L_t)^b$$

The relationship between weight and total length can be best expressed using the regression equation:

$$\text{Log } W = \text{Log } a + b \text{ Log } L_t$$

Where, W is total weight (g), L_t is total length (cm), $\text{Log } a$ and b are intercept and slope of regression line, respectively.

Condition Factor:

The well-being of dominant fish species of the Geba and Sor Rivers was investigated by using Fulton's condition factor (Leclercq, 1951; Bagenal and Tesch, 1978). Fulton's condition factor (FCF) (%) was calculated by using the following formula:

$$FCF = \frac{TW}{TL^3} \times 100$$

Where, TW - total weight (g) and TL - total length (cm).

Sex-ratio: Sex ratio was determined using the equation:

$$\text{Sex ratio} = \frac{\text{number of males}}{\text{number of females}}$$

Data Analysis:

Data were analyzed using the statistical soft-wares SPSS for Windows version 16 and Microsoft Excel for windows 7.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fish species diversity and distribution

A total of nine fish species represented in four families and seven genera were identified from Geba and Sor Rivers during the study period. The composition of fish species obtained during the study period was less diverse as compared to the results obtained by other studies in the Baro Akobo Drainage Basin (White Nile). Golubtsov *et al.* (1995) reported 90 species and Golubstov and Darkov (2008) reported 113 species from the White Nile. However, Shibru Tedla (1973) reported eight species from the White Nile. The less diversity in the present study might be due to the length of the sampling periods (i.e. this investigation was carried out in two seasons over relatively short period of time while others studies over long period), the efficiency and types of gears used, and the effect of chemicals (especially Malathions) used for fishing by fishermen (personal communications). The second reason for the less diversity reported now might be the effect of flow variability on fish assemblage. Sometimes high flows, for example, can destroy fish habitat and can wash the eggs of fish that have already been laid. The other reason might due to the fact that fish diversity decreases drastically in the upper parts of the White Nile basin like in other Ethiopian basins (Golubstov and Mina, 2003).

The diversity of fish fauna identified from the studied rivers contains a mixture of Nilo-Sudanic (*Labeo forskalii*, *Labeo cylindricus*, *B. docmak* and *M. hasselquistii*) and East African forms (*Labeobarbus intermedius*, *Labeobarbus nedgia*, *O. niloticus* and *Garra* species). The Nilo-Sudanic forms are the dominant forms in terms of diversity and are represented by a large number of species found in the Baro-Akobo Basin (Abebe Getahun, 2003). This could be probably be because of the connection between the White Nile and the two rivers. Golubtsov *et al.* (1995), Abebe Getahun (2007) and Golubstov and Darkov (2008) have reported the occurrence of these forms in the Nile basin.

Among the nine fish species identified from the two rivers, *Labeo forskalii*, *Raiamas senegalensis*, *Bagrus docmak* and *Mormyrus hasselquistii* were collected from only Geba River while *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Garra* sp. were collected from only Sor River where as *Labeobarbus intermedius*, *Labeobarbus nedgia* and *Labeo cylindricus* were recorded from both Geba and Sor Rivers. Only one endemic fish species (*Labeobarbus nedgia*) was recorded from the two rivers though it was not reported so far from Baro-Akobo basin.

The Shannon - Weiner diversity index (H') was higher in Geba River (1.50) than in Sor River (1.10). The diversity indices for the fish species indicated that there was variation in diversity between the two rivers.

Relative abundance

A total of 348 fish specimens were collected from eight sampling sites during the study period. Of the total specimens collected, 116 were caught during the wet season and 232 specimens were caught during the dry season. *Labeobarbus intermedius* was the most abundant species in number both in wet and dry seasons followed by *Labeo cylindricus*, *Labeo forskalii* and *Labeobarbus nedgia* and they contributed 47.13%, 21.84%, 12.36% and 12.36% of the total catch in number, respectively. *Raiamas senegalensis*, *Mormyrus hasselquistii* and *Garra* sp. had one specimen each and they were the least abundant fish species in number (Table 2).

The species collected were analyzed based on Index of Relative Importance (IRI), which is a measure of the relative abundance or commonness of the species based on number and weight of individuals in catches, as well as their frequency of occurrence (Kolding 1989, 1999). According to IRI the most important species in the total catches were *Labeobarbus intermedius* (48.62%), *Labeobarbus nedgia* (16.81%) and *Labeo cylindricus* (14.76%) (Table 2).

Table 2. Percentage of number, weight and Index of Relative Abundance (IRI) of fish species of Geba and Sor Rivers.

Species	N	%N	%W	%IRI
<i>Labeobarbus intermedius</i>	164	47.13	48.62	60.72
<i>Labeo cylindricus</i>	76	21.84	15.15	14.66
<i>Labeobarbus nedgia</i>	43	12.36	15.94	16.83
<i>Labeo forskalii</i>	43	12.36	12.96	6.02
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	10	2.87	1.25	0.49
<i>Bagrus docmak</i>	7	2.01	5.54	1.20
<i>Raiamas senegalensis</i>	3	0.86	0.24	0.043
<i>Garra</i> sp.	1	0.29	0.18	0.018
<i>Mormyrus hasselquistii</i>	1	0.29	0.12	0.016

The weight and number of fish specimens was higher in dry season than wet season for both rivers (Table 3). During wet season there is high turbidity, speedy run-off and low temperature that attributed to less number of fish catch during this season. There is also higher water discharge during wet season so fishes could be highly dispersed in the large volume of water than dry season and it becomes difficult to catch them (Genanaw Tesfaye, 2006). In addition, the variation in gill net efficiency and time of setting of gill net might have contributed to variation in the catches between wet and dry seasons. Moreover, leaves, logs, roots that were brought by flooding, could decrease the efficiency of gill nets during the wet season.

Table 3. Biomass of fish species during wet and dry season.

Fish species	Wet				Dry				Overall	
	Geba	Sor	Total	%	Geba	Sor	Total	%	Total	%
<i>Labeobarbus intermedius</i>	24.30	6.00	30.30	50.25	31.80	17.60	49.40	47.48	79.70	48.62
<i>Labeo cylindricus</i>	3.20	4.30	7.50	12.44	10.45	6.95	17.40	16.72	24.90	15.15
<i>Labeobarbus nedgia</i>	12.40	3.20	15.60	25.87	7.15	3.45	10.60	10.19	26.20	15.94
<i>Labeo forskalii</i>	5.70	0	5.70	9.45	15.60	0	15.60	14.99	21.30	12.96
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	0	0.70	0.70	1.16	0	1.35	1.35	1.30	2.05	1.25
<i>Bagrus docmak</i>	0	0	0	0	9.10	0	9.10	8.75	9.10	5.54
<i>Raiamas senegalensis</i>	0.40	0	0.40	0.66	0	0	0	0	0.40	0.24
<i>Garra sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0.30	0.30	0.29	0.30	0.18
<i>Mormyrus hasselquistii</i>	0	0	0	0	0.20	0	0.20	0.19	0.20	0.12

The number and weight of fish specimens in Geba River is higher than in Sor River. The difference in number and weight of fish specimens in these rivers may have been attributed to the fact that most parts of Sor River is highly irrigated and contain less vegetation cover. This, in turn, may have contributed to the lack of good habitats which contains diversity of riparian vegetations.

Length-weight relationship:

The length – weight relationship of the three species, *Labeobarbus intermedius*, *Labeo cylindricus* and *Labeobarbus nedgia* were negative allometric growth. The b-values obtained for *Labeo cylindricus* (2.72) was in agreement with the value obtained for the *Labeo forskalii* (2.76) from Angereb and Sanja Rivers, Tekeze Basin (Genanaw Tesfaye, 2006). However, the b-value obtained for *Labeobarbus intermedius* (2.50) and *Labeobarbus nedgia* (2.65) (Table 4) were less than the result obtained for *Labeobarbus intermedius* (2.96, 2.95) and *Labeobarbus nedgia* (2.94, 2.98) from River Angereb (Genanaw Tesfaye, 2006) and from Arno-Garno River (Shewit Gebremedhin, 2011), respectively. The variations of results obtained by other studies in other rivers and in the present study were probably because of the differences in number of samples, the differences in food availability, gonad development and spawning period (Bagenal and Tesch, 1978).

Table 4. Length-weight relationship of the most common fish species of Geba and Sor Rivers (ANOVA, P<0.05).

Fish species	Rivers	Regression equation	R ²	P- value	Mean ±SE TL	Mean ± SE TW
<i>Labeobarbus intermedius</i>	Geba	Wt=0.0354TL ^{2.70}	0.967	0.00	38.48±1.40	813.04±89.50
	Sor	Wt=0.01314TL ^{2.27}	0.787	0.00	26.68±0.55	249.47±21.36
<i>Labeo cylindricus</i>	Geba	Wt=0.0508TL ^{2.56}	0.924	0.00	28.52±0.73	284.37±20.90
	Sor	Wt=0.236TL ^{2.88}	0.682	0.00	31.21±0.52	401.78±22.04
<i>Labeobarbus nedgia</i>	Geba	Wt=0.0493TL ^{2.60}	0.970	0.00	43.6±2.32	977.5±123.99
	Sor	Wt=0.0258TL ^{2.70}	0.791	0.00	27.61±1.24	289.13±58.80

Fulton Condition Factor (FCF):

Condition factors parameters depend on factors including biological and environmental, as well as geographical and temporal, such as the age and condition of the fish or the season of year when samples are collected (Ferreira et al., 2008; Vaslet et al., 2008; Nowak et al., 2009). Generally, higher condition is associated with higher energy content, adequate food availability, reproductive potential and favorable environmental conditions (Pauker and Coot, 2004). The mean Fulton Condition Factor (FCF) values for *Labeobarbus intermedius* (1.21) (Table 5) was nearest to the result obtained for *Labeobarbus intermedius* (1.23) from Borkena River, Awash Basin (Asefa Tessema et al., 2012). The mean FCF value obtained for *Labeobarbus nedgia* (1.05) from Geba and Sor Rivers was less than the result obtained for *Labeobarbus nedgia* (1.48) from Rivers Angereb and Sanja, Tekeze Basin (Genanaw Tesfaye, 2006). However, the results obtained for *Labeobarbus intermedius* was greater than that reported for *Labeobarbus intermedius* (1.0, 1.12) from Beles and Gelgel Beles (Zelege Berie, 2007) and from Guang, Ayima, Gendwuha and Shinfa (Dereje Twabe, 2008), respectively. The mean FCF value obtained for *Labeo cylindricus* (1.21) was greater than the one mentioned in Angereb and Sanja Rivers, Tekeze Basin for *Labeo forskalii* (1.18) (Genanaw Tesfaye, 2006). The prior reason for the above difference in FCF might be due to lack of in-depth sampling in the present investigation. The other reason might be due to fluctuations in factors such as food quantity and quality, water level and flow rate, rate of feeding, health of fish and reproductive activity (Payne, 1986; Getachew Tefera, 1987).

Table 5. Mean \pm SE Fulton Condition Factor (FCF) for the most abundant species of Geba and Sor Rivers.

Fish species	Seasons								
	Wet		Dry						
	Mean \pm SE	FCF	N	Mean \pm SE	FCF	N	F	P	
<i>Labeobarbus intermedius</i>	1.20 \pm 0.06		50	1.22 \pm 0.03		114	164	0.127	0.722
<i>Labeo cylindricus</i>	1.10 \pm 0.05		20	1.25 \pm 0.02		56	76	9.954	0.002
<i>Labeobarbus nedgia</i>	1.03 \pm 0.03		25	1.09 \pm 0.05		18	43	1.109	0.299

Sex ratio:

From the total number of 278 most abundant fish species collected during the study period 169 (60.79%) were females and 109 (39.21%) were males. Six (2.16%) species were unsexed and excluded from the sex ratio study. Females were more numerous than males for the most abundant fish species. The chi-square test showed that there was significant difference (χ^2 P<0.05) between the number of male and female in fish species of Geba and Sor Rivers. The difference in sex ratio might be due to vulnerability of fish to fishing gears used, fishing sites (Demeke Admasu, 1994), habitat and segregation during spawning and feeding.

CONCLUSION

The fish diversity of Geba and Sor rivers is less diverse as compared to most studied rivers in Ethiopia. The fish faunal diversity of both Rivers was dominated by cyprinid fish species. The watershed of Sor River is relatively degraded. Therefore, afforestation program should be practiced around this river. Socio-economic aspects of the two rivers should be studied in detail. Training on the prospects for sustainable fish resource utilization in Geba and Sor Rivers should be given.

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